

**A STUDY ON ABSENTEEISM AMONG STUDENTS IN
DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
PERMBALUR**

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Cite This Article: S. Joshua Benaiah, R. Raja & R. Raj Kumar, "A Study on Absenteeism Among Students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Permbalur", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 5, Issue 1, Page Number 37-39, 2020.

Abstract:

The purpose of the project report entitles a study on absenteeism among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur. The study is focused on the human resource topic as its valuable resource which is of emotionally controlled and managed in every institution. This project report on study of student's absenteeism aims at examining the various reasons for absenteeism and the factors determining the reasons for the absenteeism. For this study simple random sampling method was used and took 220 samples for the study. The research decision is descriptive in nature and primary data were collected for the responds were recorded. Appropriate tools are used to supplement the analysis and interpretation. Tools like percentage analysis were used. The project report is intended to examine the master attendance record to find the rate of absenteeism and finding the reason for major absenteeism in all departments and finally to provide suggestions to improve the studies and controlling tool to reduce the absenteeism in concerned college.

Key Words: Absenteeism, Reason for Absenteeism, Awareness of Internal Marks, Measures.

Introduction:

Absenteeism is a habitual pattern of absence from a duty or obligation without good reason. Generally, absenteeism is unplanned absences. Absenteeism has been viewed as an indicator of poor individual performance, as well as a breach of an implicit contract between employee and employer. It is seen as a management problem, and framed in economic or quasi-economic terms. More recent scholarship seeks to understand absenteeism as an indicator of psychological, medical, or social adjustment to work. While occasional school absenteeism may not be problematic, excessive absenteeism has shown to have a negative impact. Students with poor attendance records are found to be at a disadvantage both academically and socially. Compared to their peers, these students are more at risk of academic under-performance and early school leaving. They are also at risk of having more restricted opportunities in terms of further education and employment, and are likely to experience social and emotional problems in adulthood. Missing school can be a habit-forming behavior and can be challenging to deal with despite growing awareness of the causes of absenteeism.

Research evidence suggests that early interventions are six times more likely to be successful than those after students' non-attendance has reached the persistent stage. Equally, there is normally one initial reason, referred to as "the trigger point", for the students' non-attendance. By the time students' absences have reached the persistent stage, there are at least several more reasons used to justify the action. There are positive and negative reinforcements regarding student absenteeism. A positive reinforcement meaning that the student will receive either more attention from their parent or guardian, or receive tangible benefits from not going to school. A negative reinforcement meaning that the student is avoiding school. Dube and Orpinas conducted a study by surveying 99 upper-elementary and middle schools, targeting students with attendance problems. Three major profiles were identified from these students. Dube and Orpinas found that 17.2 percent missed school to avoid fear, anxiety problems, or escape from social or evaluative situations.

Review of Related Literature:

Absenteeism is defined as the lack of presence of an students for a planned work. According to Geurts, Kompier and Grundemann (2000) further state that women are alleged by the media to hold lower work values because they make less serious attempts to resume work after sickness. Two final explanations mentioned by Johns (2003) are that, compared to men, women appeared to be more restless and busier during a scheduled day off. And 63 secondly that women may experience or respond more negatively or proactively to stressful or dissatisfying events at work and use time off as an adjective mechanism.

Steers and Rhodes (1978), Geurts, Kompier and Grundemann (2000), Barmby, Ercolani and Treble (2002), Johns (2003), Gimeno et al. (2004), Barham and Begun (2005) and Leaker (2008) all find a significant relation for women to be more absent than men. In line with these outcomes, a similar result between gender and absenteeism is expected in this study.

Wisconsin (2000) found that absenteeism and truancy have been a problem for administrators, teachers, parents, and students. If we require students to attend school 66 regularly between the ages of five or six and

sixteen to eighteen, as all fifty states and the District of Columbia currently do, then we must expect that some students are not going to conform to the mandatory attendance rules. Chronic absenteeism problems face many school districts. Wisconsin public schools report that 31.1% of total absences in the 1998-99 academic years were a result of truancy.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study on absenteeism among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.
- To identify the reasons for absenteeism.
- To analyse the awareness of attendance percentage in web portal.
- To analyse the various steps taken for reducing the absenteeism.

Scope of the Study:

- To study & analyze the reason for absenteeism in DSEC.
- To identify the relationship between the students attitude & morale.
- The study is conducted to know the various levels and reason for absence of students in DSEC.
- To assess student satisfaction towards the basic leave facilities provided to students by the college.

Needs and Importance:

- Track absences in real time connect with student via email & message.
- Boost personalized scheduling by giving online tests & quizzes.
- Gather feedback on teaching courses and training.
- Improve interactions viz chat & forum.
- Implement rewards for positive behavior
- Increase parent involvement

Research Methodology:

A research method is a systematic plan for conducting research. Sociologists draw on a variety of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, including experiments, survey research, participant observation, and secondary data. The sources of data used in this project report is primary data.

Primary Data:

Primary data consists of original information gathered from the sample size of 220 respondents.

Data Collection:

The data collection tool is used for the research in “Questionnaires” to get the primary data for the research.

Research Design:

A research design is the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analyzing measures of the variables specified in the problem research. The design of a study defines the study type and sub-type, research problem, hypotheses, independent and dependent variables, experimental design, and, if applicable, data collection methods and a statistical analysis plan. A research design is a framework that has been created to find answers to research questions.

Sample Design:

In the theory of finite population sampling, a sampling design specifies for every possible sample its probability of being drawn.

Research Hypothesis:

A research hypothesis is a specific, clear, and testable proposition or predictive statement about the possible outcome of a scientific research study based on a particular property of a population, such as presumed differences between groups on a particular variable or relationships between variables.

Null Hypothesis:

A null hypothesis is a type of hypothesis used in statistics that proposes that there is no difference between certain characteristics of a population (or data-generating process).

Alternative Hypothesis:

An alternative hypothesis states that there is statistical significance between two variables.

Sample Size:

Out of the available customers were selected for the study.

Sample size	-	220
Population size	-	2680
Sample area	-	Perambalur
Sample unit	-	Samples are from Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College

Statistical Tools of the Study:

Collected data was analyzed with the help of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square

- Correlation
- ANOVA

Analysis and Interpretation:

Respondents Based on Absent Affect your Academic Performance:

S.No	Particular	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	28	12.72
2	Agree	120	54.54
3	Neutral	36	16.36
4	Disagree	22	10
5	Strongly Disagree	14	6.3
	Total	220	100

Inference:

From the above table it is observed that, 12.72% respondents are strongly agree the absenteeism affect the academic performances, 54.54% respondents are agree, 16.36% respondents are neutral, 10% respondents are disagree and 6.3% respondents are strongly disagree the absenteeism affect the academic performances.

Respondents Based on Absent Affect Academic Performances:

Correlation:

Relationship between the Respondents Based on Age and Interested in Attending the Classes:

Age (X)	18	42	92	30	38
Interested in Attending Class (Y)	42	88	64	16	10

Interpretation:

There is positive correlation between the age and interested in attending the classes.

Suggestions:

- Engage in a one-on-one discussion with the student in order to identify the probable cause of his absenteeism. This information can help you to better address these issues.
- Educate the students regarding the importance of attendance, the adverse effects of absenteeism and college rules concerning the same.
- Parents should be made aware of the excess number of classes missed by their child. This can be done by arranging regular meetings and working with parents to plan out strategies best suited for their child.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the variables taken into consideration in this study were examined separated by previous studies. Correspondingly, it may prevent a clear picture of role of these variables in the student valuation contribute students' attendance and academic achievement. This study also provides some important findings for both psychological counselors and educators.

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